

A STUDY ON LISTENING SKILLS AMONG THE STUDENTS AT HIGHER EDUCATION LEVEL

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ABSTRACT

In the process of communication, listening is the ability where messages are to be received accurately and interpreted properly (Vaughn-Furlow, 2018). If there is no effective listening capability in someone, the messages are always misunderstood by them. As a result, the entire communication process is cut off and the sender of the messages also easily become frustrated or irritated. There are always two important things of listening regardless of the any language: first one is focus and other one is attention. The people, who could not comprehend the meaning while listening are the real poor listeners. Listening skills is such a skill that some people have to work harder to acheive it. At the time of listening, the most important thing is that he will be able to listen to a variety of voices at minimum time.

The present study has been conducted to measure the listening skills among 70 students from a University in West Bengal, India. The cross sectional survey method has been adopted for this present study and simple random sampling technique has been used for selecting the samples. A questionnaire developed by Dr. Muktipada Sinha (2017) has been used to collect primary data. The result revealed that the maximum number of students have shown high level of competencies in listening skills. It has also been observed that urban students have higher level of listening skills than the rural counterpart. Students from Science background have low level of Listening skills than students from Arts background. Therefore, the stream of study plays an important role in developing the listening skills. It has been also noticed that the students from English medium has performed a little better than the students from Bengali medium. These results are also statistically significant.

Keywords: Listening skills, Higher Education, Habitat, Stream of study, Medium of study.

INTRODUCTION

“The most basis and powerful way to connect to another person is to listen. Just listen. Perhaps the most important things we ever give each other are our attention.”

----- *Dr. Rachel Naomi Remen.*

Listening is a process where a message is received through ears. It involves identifying the sounds, then processing them into specific words and sentences. When someone listens, he/she listens to different individual sounds using his/her ears and then they convert these sounds as messages through their brain, which becomes meaningful to them.

In the process of communication, listening is the ability where messages are to be received accurately and interpreted properly. If there is no effective listening capability in someone, the sending of messages is always misunderstood by them. As a result, the entire communication process is cut off and the sender of the messages become frustrated easily or irritated. So, the effective listening skill is the key things to all effective communication.

“Nobody learned anything by hearing themselves speak. Wherever I go, I try to spend as much time as possible listening to the people I meet” (Richard Branson, 2015). He also frequently quotes that listening as one of the main factors behind the success of a person. Many successful leaders and entrepreneurs feel their efficient listening ability is behind their success that is very important. To be a good manager or leader, one must listen actively and empathetically, and also pay attention to the feedback receive (Gray & Robertson, 2005).

Bolton’s research (1986) claimed that 60-75% of oral communication has been ignored, misunderstood or quickly forgotten.

Following seven tips to help one to develop effective Listening skills:-

- i. Be attentive, maintain eye contact, but relaxed.
- ii. Keep an open mind and asked open-ended questions.
- iii. Ask probing questions only to ensure understanding.
- iv. Wait for the speaker to pause to ask clarifying questions.
- v. Listen to the words and try to picture what the speaker is saying.
- vi. Try to feel what the speaker is feeling.
- vii. Summarize the message and to give the speaker regular feedback.

➤ **Seven key of active Listening skills:**

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Listening is one of the most important activities that maintain and build relationship between one another. Research shows that 45% of our time is spent on listening, 30% for speaking, 16% for reading, and 9% for writing (Feyten, 1991; Burley-Allen, 1995; Nunan, 1998; Flowerdew & Millar, 2005).

Listening it is not currently a part of the literature that examines the building and maintaining of organizational relationship (Brunner, 2008). Listening is the act of hearing attentively. In general someone listen more than speak. Listening skills can be defined as an act of hearing attentively. Active listening, which is very important for effective communication (Tomlinson, 1984).

Listening skills bring success to a person in his family, society and also his workplace. If someone wants to get into a good profession, then there must be good

communication skills, management ability, planning and knowledge about sales; they need good Listening skills. Good Listening skills include understanding ability. Body language (Gestures) is also an important part of Listening skills. Eye contact with the speaker, sitting upright and being alert for all time are the good symptom of a good listener.

Simply telling a student with poor listening skills to “pay attention” is not sufficient to solve the problem (Dr. Kenneth Shore, 2005). Teacher can promote advanced Listening skills for the learners by varying the way they communicate and making some subtle changes in the classroom setting. This strategy may help and also foster to effective communication. If it is planned properly, the result will be positive.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The earlier researches mainly focus on developing Listening skills among children. This study will focus on measuring competencies in Listening skills among the students of Higher Education level. In the present research study, the researcher will focus on the following research questions:

- i. What is the existing status of Listening skills among the students at Higher Education level of in a University in West Bengal?
- ii. What are the prevalence rates of listening skills among the students at Higher Education level with respect to different socio-economic parameters?

To find out the answers of the above identified research questions, the problem of the present study was specified and stated as, *“A study on Listening Skills among the Students at Higher Education level”*.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

In the basis of these research questions and delimitations, the researcher identified the following objectives:-

- i. To find out the rate of prevalence of Listening skills among the students at Higher Education level of a University in West Bengal.
- ii. To find out the variation of impact caused by Listening skills among the students at Higher Education level in respect of different socio-economic parameters like; habitat, stream of study and medium of study.

HYPOTHESES OF THE STUDY

In view of the basic research questions, delimitations and objectives of the study, following null hypotheses were formulated:-

- ⁰H₁: There is no significant dependency in between type of habitat and listening skills among the students at Higher Education level of a University in West Bengal.
- ⁰H₂: Stream of study does not play a significant role in variation of Listening skills among the students at Higher Education level of a University in West Bengal.
- ⁰H₃: Medium of study does not seem to be a significant factor for variation of listening skills among the students at Higher Education level of a University in West Bengal.

METHODOLOGY

The present study followed quantitative research design. Cross sectional survey method has been adopted to assess the listening skills of the students at Higher Education level. The survey was conducted in a University of Paschim Medinipur district in West Bengal in India.

- **Population:** Students at undergraduate level (B.A. 1st, 2nd & 3rd year) in a University of Paschim Medinipur district in the present year were considered as population of the study.
- **Sample:** As the survey research requires a good number of participants which represent the whole population to collect relevant information from the target group. The present study was conducted among 70 undergraduate students who were randomly selected from a University of Paschim Medinipur district in West Bengal.

The summary of sample distribution was shown in table no. 1

Table no. 1: Distribution of sample according to different socio-economic parameters

Variables		Total Number	Percentage
Habitat	Rural	41	58.57%
	Urban	29	41.43%
Stream of study	Arts	46	65.71%
	Science	24	34.29%
Medium of study	Bengali	63	90%
	English	7	10%

Tools: The researcher has devised a well designed questionnaire as a tool for primary data collection from the students of undergraduate level; which was developed by Dr. Muktipada Sinha (Associate Professor and HOD, Department of Education, Jadavpur University, Kolkata, West Bengal, India). The questionnaire contains seventeen statements; against each one response i.e., ‘Yes’ or ‘No’ were to be made. There were six statements, of which if ‘Yes’ be the answer then it indicate negative response and rest eleven statements were of reverse order. The researcher has termed the former type questions as ‘negative questions’ (2, 4, 5, 14, 15 & 17) and the later types as ‘positive questions’ (1, 3, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13 & 16). The scores are divided into two categories i.e. High Listening Skills and Low Listening Skills. Those who scores bellow 11 are in Low Listening Skills category and those who score 11 & above are in High Listening Skills category.

<u>Types of Question</u>	<u>Yes</u>	<u>No</u>
1. Negative Question	0	1
2. Positive Question	1	0

ANALYSIS AND RESULT

- **Descriptive statistics:** Assessment of the overall Listening skills among the students at undergraduate level. Here out of the total 70 students; 34 i.e. 48.57% students exhibited low level of Listening skills and 36 i.e. 51.43% students showed high level of listening skills among the students at undergraduate level. The illustration was given in table no. 2 and figure no. 1.

Table no 2: Represent the overall listening skills among the students at Higher Education level.

Overall Listening Skills			Total
Listening Skills	Low level of Listening skills	Count	34
		% of total	48.57%
	High level of Listening skills	Count	36
		% of total	51.43%
		Count	70

Total	% of total	100%
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Figure no. 1:

Habitat wise comparison of the Listening skills among the students at Higher Education level:

Habitat wise analysis of the listening skills among the students at Higher Education level; scoring is given in the following table no. 3 and figure no. 2.

Overall Listening Skills			Habitat		Total
			Rural	Urban	
Listening Skills	Low level of Listening skills	Count	25	9	34
		% within habitat	68.98%	31.03%	48.57%
	High level of Listening skills	Count	16	20	36
		% within habitat	39.02%	68.97%	51.43%
		Count	41	29	70
		% within	100%	100%	100%

Total	habitat			
	% of total	58.57%	41.43%	100%

Table no. 3: Conditional distribution of Listening skills level by Habitat among the students at Higher Education:

Figure no. 2:

Stream of study wise comparison of the Listening skills among the students at Higher Education level:

Stream of study wise analysis of the Listening skills among the students at Higher Education level; scoring is given in the following table no. 4 and figure no. 3.

Table no. 4: Conditional distribution of listening skills level by Stream of study among the students at Higher Education:

Overall Listening Skills			Stream of study		Total
			Arts	Science	
Listening	Low level of Listening skills	Count	22	12	34
		% within stream	47.83%	50%	48.57%

Skills	High level of Listening skills	Count	24	12	36
		% within stream	52.17%	50%	51.43%
Total		Count	46	24	70
		% within stream	100%	100%	100%
		% of total	65.71%	34.29%	100%

Figure no. 3:

Medium of study wise comparison of the Listening skills among the students at Higher Education level:

Medium of study wise analysis of the Listening skills among the students at Higher Education level; scoring is given in the following table no. 5 and figure no. 4.

Table no. 5: Conditional distribution of Listening skills level by Medium of study among the students at Higher Education:

Figure no 4:

Overall Listening Skills			Medium of study		Total
			Bengali	English	
Listening Skills	Low level of Listening skills	Count	31	3	34
		% within medium	49.20%	42.86%	48.57%
	High level of Listening skills	Count	32	4	36
		% within medium	50.80%	57.14%	51.43%
Total		Count	63	7	70
		% within medium	100%	100%	100%
		% of total	90%	10%	100%

- **Inferential statistics:** This part of the chapter deals with inferential statistics. In the present study, the nature of population from which sample have been chosen were not known to be normal. The different types of socio-economic variables were in normal form which is classified in categories and represented by frequency counts. So, it was decided to analyze the collected data by non-parametric test, more especially Chi-square test (χ^2).
- **Hypotheses testing:**

Table no. 6: Chi-square test (χ^2) has showing different variable wise Listening skills level among the students at Higher Education level:

Chi-square Test (Pearson Chi-square)					
Sl. No.	Variables	Value	df	Asymptotic Significant (2-Sided) [p-value]	Remarks
1.	Habitat	6.096 ^a	1	0.014	S** (p<0.05)
2.	Stream of study	0.030 ^a	1	0.863	NS* (p>0.05)
3.	Medium of study	0.102 ^a	1	0.750	NS* (p>0.05)

df- Degree of Freedom, S** -Significant, NS* - Not Significant.

⁰H₁: There is no significant dependency in between type of habitat and Listening skills among the students at Higher Education level of the University in West Bengal.

- The analysis in the above table revealed that the value of χ^2 of ⁰H₁ is 6.096^a and p = 0.014. The critical values of χ^2 at 0.05 and 0.01 level of significant with 1 *df* = 3.841 and 6.635 respectively. It has been observed that the value of χ^2 is far lower than the critical value of χ^2 at 0.05 level but less than 0.01 level. So, the null hypothesis can rejected as p>0.05. However, it can be concluded that the difference which was found in level of Listening skills among the students at Higher Education level on the basis of their habitat is significant which means habitat significantly affects on student's Listening skills.

⁰H₂: Stream of study does not play a significant role in variation of Listening skills among the students at Higher Education level of the University in West Bengal.

- The analysis in the above table revealed that the value of χ^2 of ⁰H₂ is 0.030^a and $p = 0.863$. The critical values of χ^2 at 0.05 and 0.01 level of significant with 1 $df = 3.841$ and 6.635 respectively. It has been observed that the calculate value of χ^2 is far lower than the critical value of χ^2 at both levels. So, the null hypothesis can be accepted as $p > 0.05$. Hence, it can be safely concluded that the difference which was found in level of listening skills among the students at Higher Education level on the basis of their stream of study is not significant and it can be attributed to any chance factors.

⁰H₃: Medium of study does not seem to be a significant factor for variation of Listening skills among the students at Higher Education level of Vidyasagar University in West Bengal.

- The analysis in the above table revealed that the value of χ^2 of ⁰H₃ is 0.102^a and $p = 0.750$. The critical values of χ^2 at 0.05 and 0.01 level of significant with 1 $df = 3.841$ and 6.635 respectively. It has been observed that the value of χ^2 is far lower than the critical value of χ^2 at both levels. So, the null hypothesis can be accepted as $p > 0.05$. Hence, it can be safely concluded that the found difference in level of listening skills among the students at Higher Education level on the basis of their medium of study is not significant and it can be attributed to any chance factors.

FINDINGS WITH REGARD TO THE RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The major findings emerged from the present study would contribute to improvement of Listening skills among the students at Higher Education level of a University in West Bengal.

- *Prevalence rate of Listening skills among the students at Higher Education level of the University in West Bengal.*

It has been revealed from the present study that average number of students (51.43%) have high level of listening skills at Higher Education level.

- *The rate of prevalence of Listening skills among the students at Higher Education level on the basis of their Habitat:*

It has been revealed from the study that the high level of listening skills was more in urban students (68.97%) than the rural students (39.02%) and on the other hand level of listening skills was lower in rural students (68.98%) than the urban students (31.03%).

Through the findings of the study, the rate of prevalence of Listening skills was found much higher among the students from urban area as compared to the rural area. Inferential statistically the difference was found to be significant ($p < 0.05$).

➤ **The rate of prevalence of Listening skills among the students at Higher Education level on the basis of their Stream of study:**

It has been revealed from the study that the high level of Listening skills was more in Arts stream of students (52.17%) than Science stream of students (50%) and on the other hand low level of Listening skills was more in the students from Science stream (50%) than the students from Arts stream (47.83%).

Through the findings of the study, the rate of prevalence of Listening skills was found little higher among the students from Arts stream as compared to the Science stream. Inferential statistically the difference was found to be not significant ($p > 0.05$).

➤ **The rate of prevalence of Listening skills among the students at Higher Education level on the basis of their Medium of study:**

It has been revealed from the study that the high level of listening skills was more in the students from English medium (57.14%) than the students from Bengali medium (50.80%) and on the other hand, low level of listening skills was more in the students from Bengali medium (49.20%) than the students from English medium (42.86%).

Through the findings of the study, the rate of prevalence of listening skills was found little higher among the students from English medium as compared to the students from Bengali medium. Inferential statistically the difference was found to be not significant ($p > 0.05$).

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

The major findings emerged from the present study would be important contributions for improvement of our understanding about listening skills of the students at Higher Education level. The study investigated the rate of listening skills with respect to different socio-economic parameters viz. habitat, stream of study and medium of study.

In the present study the result revealed that, the rate of listening skills was found higher among the students from urban area as compared to the rural counterpart, It was also significant by Inferential Statistics ($p < 0.05$). The reason for the outcome of such

result was that urban students mainly grow up in a quiet natural environment, messages transmitted during the communication process are usually not distorted. Therefore, students from the urban area have to develop the ability to listen attentively to overcome all barriers of noise.

The students from Arts stream showed better listening skills than Science stream of students at Higher Education level. The results was not significant by Inferential statistics ($p>0.05$). It is now found that most of the subjects in Science stream developed bases on the practical, but the subject matter of the Arts stream is based on theory. As a result, the students of the Arts stream listen to theories (Subject matter) carefully while teaching in the classroom, as they have no opportunity for practical issues. For this reason, the students of the Arts stream show greater Listening skills than the students in the Science stream.

It has been noticed that the prevalence rate of Listening skills was more among the students from English medium than the students from Bengali medium. Inferential statistically the difference was found to be not significant ($p>0.05$). This may be considered to be the reason for such a result, in many cases, fear of the English language is noticed in Bengali speaking students. They have to work hard to learn English as English is not their mother tongue. Learning something requires first focusing, as well as Listening skills. That's why those who want to learn English, they should listen carefully Later on, those who study through English medium have the same listening skills and grow more.

In the communication process, listening is the ability to receive messages accurately and to interpret it properly. The effective listening skill is a skill that underpins all kinds of positive human relationships. In the system of education, the importance of listening skills is immeasurable. In addition to classroom situation, it has considerable impact on the administration of education as well. Despite the impact of listening skills on the overall communication system, the research paper only mentions its special importance in education, because education is the backbone of society; it plays an impactful role in the formation of a nation. In the case, if messages are misinterpreted due to a lack of careful listening skills, the communication process fails this is applicable for any communication process. If there is a lack of proper listening skills in the classroom, it can affect teaching-learning situation, which is not desirable. In present day situation, the lack of proper listening skills of students in the classroom is reducing their success rate by hindering them from their learning. As a result, the number of quality student is declining, as well as education losing its aristocracy.

The policy makers administrators, teachers, teacher-educators, intellectual persons and educationists may adopt some realistic strategies and technique which will enhance

the listening skills of the students in the light of present study. Finally, it is necessary to remove the barriers behind the development of students' listening skills as soon as possible.

LIMITATIONS AND SUGGESTIONS FOR FURTHER RESEARCH

Further studies can address the following issues to have more insights on the subject. The present study on "*A Study on Listening Skills among the Students at Higher Education level*" is not an end in itself, rather it is an on-going journey to reveal the scenario of listening among the students at Higher Education level this study opens up new grounds for further researches. Looking at the overall research study, it can be observed that there is still further scope for research in the following areas:

- a. The present study is restricted to undergraduate students only. A similar study may be conducted on Secondary or Higher secondary school students and Post-graduate students also.
- b. The present study is restricted to only Paschim Medinipur district. A similar research may also be conducted in other districts of West Bengal.
- c. The present study is a quantitative research design. It can be studied by applying qualitative research design also.
- d. The study is restricted to rural and urban areas students.
- e. The study is restricted to only three socio-economic parameters. It can be studied by applying any other socio-economic parameters.
- f. A similar study may be conducted on students with special needs and gifted children.

Therefore, numerous further studies can be conducted by the researchers to measure the multiple dimension of listening skills with the help of several statistical analysis. That's why the researcher thinks that the present study is very important in the present scenario.

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